

Received Signal Strength Gradient Estimation for Mobile Networks

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Abstract—This paper considers the question: As a receiver moves along a trajectory, is its received signal strength (RSS) increasing or decreasing? This is an important question for mobile receivers to answer in order to maintain or improve connectivity within the network. When signal strength maps are unavailable a priori, a receiver decides the answer based on its observations. We derive the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of signal strength at a particular location in Rayleigh/Rician fading and additive Gaussian noise. We estimate the slope of the gradient by making RSS estimates at multiple locations. By making estimates of the MLE variance, we can derive confidence in the gradient, which can be used to decide future movements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile networks have been the subject of intense interest in the past decade, but generally the communications enable the mobility. That is, receivers move to complete their objectives and the network adapts to the time-varying channel (e.g., forming and breaking links, re-routing packets, adapting modulation schemes). We study the estimation of received signal strength (RSS) gradient so mobility can support the communications by improving connectivity [1] or localize a signal source [2][3], among other possibilities. Because of fading effects, a small change in receiver position can cause a large fluctuation in signal strength. Some mobility strategies to improve RSS are studied in [4].

The main idea of this paper is to estimate RSS gradients by removing small-scale fading effects. Some past approaches towards gradient estimation simply assumed away the fading by averaging [2][3]. A recent study has tried to characterize the RSS environment in a detailed manner [5]. A nonparametric approach to learning RSS maps using Gaussian processes is given by Fink et al. [6]. Rather than try to precisely characterize a possibly non-stationary environment, we are interested only in estimating the RSS gradient along a trajectory in order to exploit it, e.g., for source localization.

For a fixed position, we form the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of the RSS given a set of independent measurements. These independent samples may be obtained with different frequency bands, for example. We assume a Rayleigh/Rician fading model with additive Gaussian noise and assume that the sensor can estimate the received SNR and Rician K factor [7][8]. While this model may not be a perfect fit for a particular environment (a distribution with more parameters, e.g., Nakagami, may do better), it remains a reasonable model for unknown situations and on average over many environments. An information-theoretic criterion

is used in [9] to support the Rayleigh/Rician distributions over Nakagami, Weibull, or lognormal, and the same study contains an interesting discussion on channel model selection and rejection.

We use linear regression to estimate the slope of the gradient of RSS estimates performed over many locations. We derive approximations of the RSS MLE variance and use them to calculate the variance of the gradient estimate. We then assign confidence to the gradient estimate that enables the receiver to determine its best course of action.

II. SIGNAL MODEL

Suppose the source transmits a known pilot signal $s(t)$ with support $[0, T]$ through a Rician channel. The receiver observes the signal

$$x(t) = Chs(t) + w(t) \quad (1)$$

where C represents the fixed but unknown RSS at the receiver, h is an unknown complex Gaussian variable that represents the flat fading, and $w(t)$ is a complex white Gaussian noise process with power spectral density $\frac{1}{2}N_0$. In addition to path loss, C also encapsulates any shadowing that the signal may experience at the receiver.

We assume synchronization at the receiver so that the matched filter output is given by

$$\tilde{x} = \frac{\int_0^T s^*(t)x(t)dt}{\int_0^T s^*(t)s(t)dt} \quad (2)$$

$$= Ch + \frac{\int_0^T s^*(t)w(t)dt}{\|s\|^2} = Ch + w \quad (3)$$

where we implicitly define $w = \frac{\int_0^T s^*(t)w(t)dt}{\|s\|^2}$. Since integration is a linear operation, w is a complex Gaussian variable with zero mean and variance $\sigma_w^2 = \frac{N_0}{\|s\|^2}$. Thus the receiver observes the RSS C with a random fade h in additive noise w .

III. RSS ESTIMATE

We assume that the receiver observes the complex scalar as in equation (3). At a particular location, we assume that C is constant but the fade h is random. If multiple observations are made with independent realizations of h , we can mitigate the fading. For example, with sufficient spacing, different frequencies can experience independent fades.

In the following we derive the ML estimate and its variance which we will use in Section IV to derive the RSS gradient estimator and an algorithm to estimate its accuracy.

A. Mitigating Fading

Suppose that the receiver is able to obtain N_h observations with independent fades at a fixed location. We assume the following observation model

$$y_i = Ch_i + w_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_h \quad (4)$$

where h_i, w_i are complex Gaussian random variables with respective variances σ_h^2, σ_w^2 . We allow h to have a possibly non-zero complex mean μ according to the Rayleigh/Rician model. We define $\text{SNR} = C^2(|\mu|^2 + \sigma_h^2)/\sigma_w^2$, the Rician K-factor $K = |\mu|^2/\sigma_h^2$, and $\sigma_y^2 = C^2\sigma_h^2 + \sigma_w^2$.

We want to estimate the RSS C . Without a prior on C , we cannot obtain a MMSE estimate, so we make an ML estimate based on the fading and noise statistics. The independent observations $\underline{y} = \{y_1, \dots, y_{N_h}\}$ have the multivariate Gaussian density

$$f(\underline{y}) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma_y^2)^{N_h}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{\sigma_y^2} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i - C\mu|^2\right). \quad (5)$$

The likelihood equation is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial C} \log p(\underline{y}) \Big|_{C=\hat{C}_{ML}(\underline{y})} &= 0 \\ &= \frac{2\sigma_h^2 N_h}{\sigma_y^4} [-C^3 W - C^2 X - CY + Z] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$W = \sigma_h^2 \quad (7)$$

$$X = \frac{1}{N_h} \left[\Re(\mu^* \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} y_i) \right] \quad (8)$$

$$Y = \sigma_w^2(1 + K) - \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i|^2 \quad (9)$$

$$Z = \frac{\sigma_w^2}{\sigma_h^2} X. \quad (10)$$

\hat{C}_{ML} is found by finding the largest real root of the cubic polynomial in (6).

The MLE is biased because of the root-finding. However, since the observations are i.i.d., the process is ergodic and the sample mean converges to the expectation,

$$\lim_{N_h \uparrow \infty} [-C^3 W - C^2 X - CY + Z] = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$E[-C^3 W - C^2 X - CY + Z]_{C=\hat{C}_{ML}(\underline{y})} = 0 \quad (12)$$

where

$$E[W] = \sigma_h^2 \quad (13)$$

$$E[X] = \sigma_h^2 K C \quad (14)$$

$$E[Y] = \sigma_w^2 (K - \text{SNR}) \quad (15)$$

$$E[Z] = \sigma_w^2 K C. \quad (16)$$

Fig. 1. The variance and mean-square error of \hat{C} are close for various K and SNR, so bias of the MLE is minor. The actual RSS value is $C = 1$.

Since $\hat{C}_{ML} = C$ satisfies (12), we see that $E[\hat{C}_{ML}] = C$ and hence \hat{C}_{ML} is asymptotically unbiased.

Figure 1 shows that the variance and MSE of the ML estimate \hat{C}_{ML} are close. Many other examples show similar results. Therefore \hat{C}_{ML} is a reasonable estimator whose bias does not play a major role. As expected, variance decreases as better observations of the signal are available, either through higher SNR or stronger LOS components (higher K).

B. Cramer-Rao Bound

Though the MLE is biased, Figure 1 shows that the bias is typically small. We are interested in whether the MLE's variance is close to the Cramer-Rao lower bound (CRB). The CRB is

$$\text{Var}(\hat{C}) \geq \frac{1}{I_C} = \text{CRB}(C) \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_C &= -E_C \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial C^2} \log p(\underline{y}) \right] \\ &= \frac{2\sigma_h^2}{\sigma_y^4} E_C [3C^2 W + 2CX + Y] \\ &\quad - \frac{8C\sigma_h^4}{\sigma_y^6} E_C [C^3 W + C^2 X + CY - Z] \\ &= \frac{2\sigma_h^2 N_h}{\sigma_y^4} \left(3C^2 E[W] + 2CE[X] + E[Y] \right) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

and the second term drops out because of (12).

Figure 2 shows that the variance of \hat{C}_{ML} is close to the CRB in high SNR regimes. For a particular RSS value C , increased line of sight (LOS) power allows more accurate estimates. However, as the RSS increases, the estimates become less accurate due to increased variability.

Fig. 2. The variance of the ML estimate \hat{C}_{ML} is close to the Cramer-Rao lower bound when C is not close to 0.

C. Estimator Variance when in NLOS

The variance of \hat{C}_{ML} is not close to the CRB in non-line-of-sight (NLOS), low SNR regimes. To see this, we expand (17) and (18) to write

$$\text{CRB}(C) = \frac{(C^2\sigma_h^2 + \sigma_w^2)^2}{2N_h\sigma_h^2[C^2\sigma_h^2(2+K) + \sigma_w^2K]} \quad (19)$$

When $K \neq 0$, then $\lim_{C \downarrow 0} \text{CRB} = \frac{\sigma_w^2}{2N_h\sigma_h^2K}$. However, when $K = 0$, the LOS component disappears and $\lim_{C \downarrow 0} \text{CRB}$ scales like $1/C^2$, so the CRB increases rapidly as C becomes small. For an unbiased estimator this would indicate that the observation contains almost no information. However, the ML estimate is biased and it is clear from Figure 3 that the CRB does not accurately predict MLE behavior under NLOS conditions.

We therefore want to estimate the variance of $\hat{C}_{ML} = E[\hat{C}_{ML}^2] - E[\hat{C}_{ML}]^2$. In NLOS regimes ($K = 0$), equation (6) reduces to

$$\hat{C} \left(\hat{C}^2 - \frac{1}{N_h\sigma_h^2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i|^2 - N_h\sigma_w^2 \right) \right) = 0 \quad (20)$$

\hat{C} is non-zero when $\sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i|^2 > N_h\sigma_w^2$, and therefore

$$\hat{C}^2 = \frac{1}{\sigma_h^2} \left(\frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i|^2 - \sigma_w^2 \right) \quad (21)$$

$$E[\hat{C}^2] = \frac{N_h\sigma_h^2}{\frac{1}{2}\sigma_y^2} \int_0^\infty a f_{\chi^2} \left(\frac{aN_h\sigma_h^2 + N_h\sigma_w^2}{\frac{1}{2}\sigma_y^2}, 2N_h \right) dx$$

where $\sigma_y^2 = C^2\sigma_h^2 + \sigma_w^2$ and $f_{\chi^2}(\cdot, k)$ is the probability density function of the standard χ^2 variable with k degrees of freedom.

Now consider the calculation of $E[\hat{C}]$, where

$$\hat{C} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_h} |y_i|^2}{N_h\sigma_h^2} - \frac{\sigma_w^2}{\sigma_h^2}} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 3. When in a low SNR and NLOS ($K = 0$) regime, the NLOS approximation is close to $\text{Var}[\hat{C}_{ML}]$. We show the variance for different values of the RSS C .

When $\sigma_w^2 = 0$, $\sqrt{\frac{N_h\sigma_h^2}{C^2\sigma_h^2 + \sigma_w^2}} \hat{C}$ has a standard χ distribution with $2N_h$ degrees of freedom, and therefore the expectation is

$$E_0[\hat{C}] = \sqrt{\frac{C^2\sigma_h^2 + \sigma_w^2}{N_h\sigma_h^2}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{2\pi} (2N_h - 1)!!}{2^{N_h} (N_h - 1)!} \right] \quad (23)$$

where $(\cdot)!!$ is the double factorial defined as $(2n - 1)!! \triangleq \prod_{j=1}^n (2j - 1)$. Using the first few terms of the Taylor series expansion we can obtain the approximation

$$E[\hat{C}] \approx E_0[\hat{C}] - \frac{d}{2E_0[\hat{C}]} - \frac{d^2}{8E_0[\hat{C}]^3} - \dots \quad (24)$$

Figure 3 shows that this approximation is close to the MLE variance in NLOS, low SNR regimes.

IV. GRADIENT ESTIMATION

Suppose that for each location in a linear trajectory, we have an estimate of the RSS and its corresponding variance. In the following we use these estimates to calculate the gradient of the RSS and confidence in its sign, i.e., how certain we are that the RSS is increasing or decreasing.

A. 1-D Gradient Slope Estimation

We want to estimate the RSS gradient using the RSS estimates $\{\hat{C}(m)\}$ taken at positions $\{x(m)\}$, for $1 \leq m \leq M$. A linear fit to the gradient is reasonable for small changes in $x(m)$, and more generally when m is small. When m or Δx are too large, the linear fit can smooth the gradient excessively and obscure detail.

Least-squares linear regression with uniform weighting yields the following gradient estimate \hat{a} :

$$\hat{a} = \frac{\sum_m (x(m) - \bar{x}) \hat{C}(m)}{\sum_m (x(m) - \bar{x})^2} \quad (25)$$

The variance of the slope estimate \hat{a} is [10]

$$\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2 = \frac{\sum_m (x(m) - \bar{x})^2 \text{Var}[C(m)]}{[\sum_m (x(m) - \bar{x})^2]^2} \quad (26)$$

where $\bar{\cdot}$ indicates arithmetic mean.

B. Confidence in RSS Gradient

In order to calculate a confidence level on the RSS gradient, the receiver needs to calculate $\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2$ using (26) which requires $\text{Var}[\hat{C}(m)]$. However, the variance depends on the actual RSS $C(m)$, which the sensor does not know. We therefore approximate $C(m) \approx \hat{C}(m)$.

Good approximations for $\text{Var}[\hat{C}(m)]$ are given for LOS (Section III-B) and NLOS (Section III-C) regimes; a method for distinguishing between the two regimes is given in [11]. For example, if the receiver is in a LOS situation, it substitutes $\text{Var}[\hat{C}(m)] \approx \text{CRB}[\hat{C}(m)]$ in equation (25).

Given the slope variance $\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2$, we can also calculate a confidence level for the sign of the slope. With approximately Gaussian distributed slope estimates, a simple calculation based on its estimated slope and variance is

$$P(\text{sign error}) = \Phi(|E[\hat{a}]/\sigma_{\hat{a}}|) \quad (27)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard Gaussian CDF and $\hat{a}, \sigma_{\hat{a}}^2$ are the slope and its corresponding variance defined in Section IV-A.

C. Gradient Estimation Algorithm

The RSS gradient estimation is comprised of the following steps:

- 1) For each position in $\{x(m)\}$
 - a) Take N_h independent measurements (4)
 - b) Estimate $\hat{C}(m)$ (6)
 - c) Estimate $\text{Var}[C(m)]$ (Section III-B or III-C)
- 2) Calculate gradient estimate \hat{a} (25)
- 3) Calculate gradient variance $\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2$ (26)
- 4) Calculate gradient confidence (27)

With the gradient and corresponding confidence level, the receiver is able to exploit the gradient information to assist in its tasks.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

We adopt the following propagation model [12] for the simulations.

$$C_i = P_t \left[\frac{d_i}{d_0} \right]^{-\alpha} \quad (28)$$

where d_i is the distance from the signal source, d_0 is the reference distance, and α is the path loss exponent. We fix the trajectory of a measurement campaign and vary the transmit power P_t to study the performance of the gradient estimation.

We first simulate outdoor conditions with the receiver making RSS measurements at co-linear locations [200, 210, 220, 230] λ from the signal source. For a 2.4 GHz signal, for example, this is equivalent to distances of [25, 26.25, 27.5, 28.75] meters. In figure 4, we vary the received SNR and see that the variance of the gradient and its estimate (25) are

Fig. 4. The variance of the gradient estimate improves in higher SNR and for environments with stronger LOS (higher K). Measurement positions are [200,210,220] λ from the signal source.

in agreement. Figure 5 shows the probability of deciding the correct sign of the RSS gradient. It is clear that channels with a stronger LOS component (μ of the channel h in (4)) yield better gradient estimates.

Figure 5 also shows the discrepancy between the probability of deciding the correct gradient sign and our approximation given in equation (27). When the strengths are known, the performance can be calculated precisely. Therefore, the discrepancy between the actual performance and our pessimistic estimate is due to the inability of the receiver to know the actual RSS and the subsequent approximation of $C(m) \approx \hat{C}(m)$. This results in a higher estimate for the variance and hence a more pessimistic view of the gradient estimate quality.

We next consider indoor conditions, where the receiver may be closer to the source and may be restricted to making smaller movements between measurements. We consider the co-linear locations [50,55,60] λ from the signal source, or equivalently [6.25, 6.875, 7.5] meters for a 2.4 GHz signal. Note that for a fixed separation between locations, a larger change in RSS will be measured when the receiver is closer to the source (28). Figure 6 shows that though the distance between measurements has been halved (cf. Figure 5), the decreased distance to the source actually gives the receiver much higher confidence in the gradient sign.

VI. CONCLUSION

With knowledge of simple channel statistics, we have shown a method of estimating the RSS gradient as a mobile receiver moves along a linear trajectory. We derived the maximum likelihood estimate of RSS to mitigate the effects of fading and additive noise. We then estimate the RSS gradient across multiple positions using linear regression. The variance of the gradient is estimated and used to predict the accuracy of the gradient direction. Our confidence of the gradient sign is pessimistic and the actual performance can be much

Fig. 5. The probability of incorrectly estimating the gradient sign (increasing vs. decreasing RSS) is improved for environments with stronger LOS (higher K). The estimated error probability based on \hat{C} is pessimistic because of the increased uncertainty. Measurement positions are $[200,210,220,230] \lambda$ from the signal source.

Fig. 6. The probability of incorrectly estimating the gradient sign (increasing vs. decreasing RSS) is improved when the receiver is closer to the source. Measurement positions are $[50,55,60] \lambda$ from the signal source.

higher than we predict. Simulations show that better gradient estimates can be obtained by increasing either the number or physical spacing of independent RSS measurements.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Hsieh, A. Cowley, V. Kumar, and C. J. Taylor, "Maintaining network connectivity and performance in robot teams," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 25, no. 1-2, pp. 111–131, 2008.
- [2] Y. Sun, J. Xiao, X. Li, and F. Cabrera-Mora, "Adaptive Source Localization by a Mobile Robot Using Signal Power Gradient in Sensor Networks," in *IEEE GLOBECOM 2008*, November 2008, pp. 1–5.
- [3] D. Han, D. G. Andersen, M. Kaminsky, K. Papagiannaki, and S. Seshan, "Access Point Localization using Local Signal Strength Gradient," in *Passive & Active Measurement (PAM)*, Seoul, South Korea, Apr. 2009.

- [4] J. Smith, M. Olivieri, A. Lackpour, and N. Hinnerschitz, "RF-mobility gain: concept, measurement campaign, and exploitation," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 38–44, February 2009.
- [5] Y. Mostofi, M. Malmirchegini, and A. Ghaffarkhah, "Estimation of communication signal strength in robotic networks," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2010, pp. 1946–1951.
- [6] J. Fink and V. Kumar, "Online methods for radio signal mapping with mobile robots," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2010, pp. 1940–1945.
- [7] N. Shroff and K. Giridhar, "Biased estimation of Rician K factor," in *International Conference on Information, Communications Signal Processing (ICICSP)*, 2007, pp. 1–5.
- [8] A. Abdi, C. Tepedelenlioglu, M. Kaveh, and G. Giannakis, "On the estimation of the K parameter for the Rice fading distribution," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 92–94, March 2001.
- [9] U. Schuster and H. Bolcskei, "Ultrawideband Channel Modeling on the Basis of Information-Theoretic Criteria," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 2464–2475, July 2007.
- [10] N. Draper and H. Smith, *Applied Regression Analysis*, 3rd ed., ser. A Wiley-Interscience publication. New York, NY: Wiley, 1998.
- [11] S. Gezici, H. Kobayashi, and H. Poor, "Non-parametric non-line-of-sight identification," in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC)*, vol. 4, Oct 2003, pp. 2544–2548.
- [12] A. Goldsmith, *Wireless Communications*. New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press, 2005.